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**Knowledge and Attitude Regarding
Substance Abuse of Adolescents Among
High School and Higher Secondary
School Teachers in Selected Schools at
Thiruvananthapuram**

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ABSTRACT

Substance abuse is a term which is used to define as an addictive disorder that describes a pattern of substance use leading to significant, problems, activities, substance use in dangerous situations, substance related legal problems or continued substance use that interferes with friendship or family relationships. This study was conducted to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding substance abuse of adolescents among high school and higher secondary teachers in selected schools at Thiruvananthapuram. The study's goals are to determine how well-informed teachers in particular schools are about teen substance addiction. To assess the attitude regarding substance abuse of adolescents among school teachers, to find out the correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding substance abuse of adolescents among school teachers. The finding shows that most of the subjects belonged in the age group of 25 – 35 years. 74.6% of the subjects were females and 25.4% of subject were males. Among these, 74.6% of the subjects have B. ED qualifications. Majority 55.6%, have 1-5 years' experience. Out of 100% 63.5% having previous knowledge regarding substance abuse. Majority 68.3% have good knowledge. Also 50.8% have positive attitude towards substance abuse, 49.2% have negative attitude towards substance abuse. The result revealed that the majority of the teachers had good knowledge regarding substance abuse and positive attitude towards substance abuse. When the level of knowledge increases, attitude also increases. So, there is a strong positive relation between knowledge and attitude.

Keywords: Substance abuse, adolescent, knowledge, attitude

INTRODUCTION

Human life completes its journey through various stages and most vital stage is adolescence. The time between childhood and adulthood is known as adolescence. During this transition dramatic physical, cognitive psychosocial and psychosexual changes take place that are existing and at the same time threatful. The use of dangerous or harmful psychoactive substances, such as alcohol, tobacco, and other illegal narcotics like opiates, heroin, cannabis, amphetamine, and many more, is referred to as substance abuse. Adolescence is the crucial period when the initiation of substance abuse takes place, they are particularly vulnerable due to various reasons like academic pressure, temptation by peer group etc.[1]

High school teachers, as front-line educators and mentors, plays pivotal role shaping adolescent behavior and attitudes. Their ability to identify early signs of substance use, understand the associated complications and implement effective preventions strategies is essential in curbing the rise of this issue. Teachers often serve as the first point of contact and influence outside the family, placing them in a unique position to intervene effects.[2]

Adolescent substance misuse must be prevented by focusing on modifiable risk factors and raising awareness of traits that put young people at risk. Finding risk factors for teen drug and alcohol use has been the focus of numerous studies. Teenage usage of alcohol and other drugs has long been a public health concern. A worrying percentage of teenagers satisfy the criteria for a substance use problem and would significantly benefit from receiving high-quality treatment, even

while some substance use may be psychologically regular.[3]

RESEARCH PROBLEM

A descriptive study to evaluate high school and upper secondary school teachers' attitudes and knowledge on teen substance misuse in a few Thiruvananthapuram schools.[4,5]

OBJECTIVES

- To find out what teachers in particular schools know about teen substance misuse.
- To find out how teachers feel about teen substance abuse.
- To determine the relationship between school instructors' attitudes and knowledge about teen substance usage.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Quantitative research approach and a descriptive research design were adopted to accomplish the study objectives. Convenient sampling technique was used to select 63 high school and higher secondary teachers at selected schools at Thiruvananthapuram. Permission was taken from the higher authorities of high school and higher secondary schools at Thiruvananthapuram. A sampling frame was prepared for those who fulfil the inclusive criteria of the current study. Researchers explained the main aim of the study.[6,7]

Specification of the Instrument and Related Measurement

Section A: Socio demographic data consists of 5 items (age, gender, qualification, experience, previous knowledge)[8,9]

Section B: Semi structured knowledge assessment questionnaire

Instrument consists of 20 multiple choice questions to assess the level of knowledge regarding substance abuse. Each question has one right answer and three distracters, each right answer carries one mark. The total knowledge questionnaire score was 20 and graded as good, average and poor.[10,11]

Section C: Self structured Attitude rating scale

Instrument consists of 10 items with 5-point like scale to assess the attitude regarding substance abuse. The maximum score expected was 50 and minimum score was 10. Measurement of perception score was divided into three categories like positive attitude, neutral attitude and negative attitude.[12,13]

RESULTS

This section deals with the percentage and frequency distribution of 63 sample regarding age in years, gender, qualification, year of experience and previous knowledge. Among 63 samples, majority of subjects 55.6% belongs to 25-35 years of age, 30.2% belongs to 36-45 years of age and 6.3% belongs to 56-60 years of age. Majority 74.6% were female subjects and 25.4% were male subjects. Subjects based on qualifications: 74.6% B.Ed, 9.5% MSc, 7.9% BSc and M.Ed. Subjects based on experience 55.6% of teachers have 1-5 years, 25.45 teachers have 6-10 years, and 19% teachers have 11-20 years of experience. Majority 63.55 of subjects have previous knowledge.

Table 1: Showing the frequency and percentage distribution of subjects according to socio personal variables among school teachers. n=63

S. No	Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage	
1.	Age (years)	25 – 35 years	35	55.6
		36 - 45 years	19	30.2
		46 - 55 years	5	7.9
		56 - 60	4	6.3
2.	Gender	Male	16	25.4
		Female	47	76.6
3.	Qualification	B. ED	47	74.6
		BSC	5	7.9
		MSC	6	9.5
		M.ED	5	7.9
4.	Experience	1-5	35	55.6
		6-10	16	25.4
		11-20	12	19
5.	Previous knowledge	Yes	40	63.5
		No	23	36.5

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects based on level of knowledge regarding substance abuse. n=63.

Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Good	43	68.3
Average	18	28.6
Poor	2	3.2

Table 2: Shows that 43 subjects (68.3%) had good knowledge, 18 subjects (28.6%) had average knowledge, and 2 subjects (3.2%) had poor knowledge.

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects based on level of attitude regarding substance abuse among school teachers n=63

Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Positive	32	50.8
Negative	31	49.2

Table 3 shows that 32 subjects (50.8%) had positive attitude, and 31 subjects (49.2%) had negative attitude regarding substance abuse.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of knowledge and attitude regarding substance abuse n=63.

Variable	Mean (x)	Standard Deviation
Knowledge	15.07	4.30
Attitude	39.19	5.54

Table 4 shows that mean and standard deviation of knowledge is 15.07 and 4.30 respectively and mean and standard deviation of attitude is 39.19 and 5.54 respectively.

Table 5: Correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding substance abuse among school teachers.

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation	Pearson's correlation	P value
Knowledge	15.07	4.30	0.345	<0.001
Attitude	39.19	5.54		

Table V shows that Pearson's correlation is 0.345 and the P value is less than 0.001. With regards to the mean and standard deviation of knowledge, results were 15.07 ± 4.30 respectively and the mean and standard deviation of attitude results were 39.19 ± 5.54 respectively. Table shows that attitude increases with level of knowledge. So there is significant relation between knowledge and attitude.

DISCUSSION

The study showed most of the subjects belonged in the age group of 25-35 years 74.6% of the subject were females and 25.4% of the subjects were males. Among these 74.6% of the subjects have B. Ed qualification. Majority 55.6% have 1-5 year experience. 63.5% have previous knowledge regarding substance abuse. The study is in accordance with findings of another study "A study to assess knowledge attitude and practice of school

personnel on COPTA" a cross sectional questionnaire based study carried out on a convenient sampling of 100 school personnel aged 25-60 years. Among these 69.2% of subjects were females and 30.8% of subjects were males. 74.6% have previous knowledge regarding substance abuse.

In knowledge assessment it was estimated that 68.3% have good knowledge regarding substance abuse. Similar study conducted in PU college Bangalore, out of 40 subjects 75% of teachers have good knowledge.

In attitude assessment 50.8% of teachers have positive attitude towards substance abuse and 49.2% have negative attitude towards substance abuse. A matched study at Assuit University revealed the "knowledge and attitude of secondary school teachers towards substance abuse among the students." Regarding substance

usage, 74.1% have a good attitude and 25.9% have a negative view.

CONCLUSION

The presented study was aimed to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding substance abuse of adolescents among high school and higher secondary school teachers in selected schools at Thiruvananthapuram. The result shows that majority 68.3% have good knowledge also 50.8% have positive attitude towards substance abuse and 49.2% have negative attitude towards substance abuse.

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